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Democratic Backsliding and Rising Authoritarianism under the Guise of Electoral Process: Case-Study of Pakistan

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Abstract

Competitive authoritarianism and democratic deficit are the problems faced by the contemporary world. Although, the autocratic regimes, too, contain democratic structures including a functional parliament, independent media and provision of fundamental human rights ensured through the existing constitutional instruments but, in essence, the democracy and democratic spirit remain nonexistent in such societies. A deeper insight into such political systems reveals that the political parties pretend as working independently and exercising political

power through the chosen leadership but intrinsically the power is vested somewhere else that is in those institutions which, although, are established to defend the geographical boundaries of the state but the inept democratic leadership provide them space through its exercise of power in such a way to accomplish and accumulate personal wealth hence such state institutions have to intervene so that the very basic structure of the state might remain intact. Pakistan is also not an exemption in this regard where the democratic regimes continuously disappointed the general public for not satisfying their basic needs and not adopting any long term economic policy which would meaningfully resolve the problems faced by them. In that background, the instant study analyzes the state of democratic governance in Pakistan being applied currently and which had been followed in recent past. It finds that true democracy never existed in Pakistan whereas it is the need of the hour for the state of Pakistan to respect the popular will reflected through the electoral process.

Keywords: Democratic Deficit, Hybrid Regime, Democratization, Democratic Backsliding

1. Introduction

Democracy has been regarded as an ideal tool for socio-political development and the driving force behind prosperity of the modern states. It is commonly regarded as systematic relationship between representatives

and the citizenry, grounded in the fundamentals of equity, individual liberties and participation. Traditionally, democracy has been associated with the protection of civil rights and the establishment of mechanisms that ensure equality before the law. Unfortunately, according to an assessment report of the Global State of Democracy, democratic institutions and civil liberties have been under the decline. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) identifies the phenomenon of the democratic deficit as a deviation from essential of democracy, characterized by limited political participation, lack of openness and weakened commitment to rule of law. Furthermore, Freedom House, a US think tank, warns that “global freedom faces a dire threat” as increasing mistrust in governments and representative institutions undermines public engagement and trust over democracies. The deficit is not only confined to traditional democracies but also deeply impacted newly established states. The emergence of new autocratic order has deliberately eroded democratic values since it believes in executing aggressive measures to stay in power (Ekiert, 2023).

The democratic erosion refers to gradual decline in both the quality and functioning of democratic systems. Such erosion can occur incrementally within the framework of existing democratic institutions or manifest through sudden authoritarian takeovers (Khan & Kaunert, 2024). In the modern world, the authoritarian rulers seek legitimacy through elections, marginalizing opposition and representative institutions systematically. The new trends in hybrid regimes blend democratic procedures with authoritarian practices or using repressive methods to rule. It is the indicator of democratic regression which points towards undermining of democratic institutions such as executive, judiciary and election commission in which the shell of democracy remains but likely to shorn of substance.

Similarly, scholars apply another term denoted as “dictatorial drift” to express an aggressive tendency used against domestic opponents. The present situation of democratic deficit has several new features when compared with the past; in contemporary state of affairs, the intensity and scale of democratic erosion make it different today. For example, in the case of Pakistan, military has provided soft corner for democratic institutions to function and preserved its critical role when political crisis needed to be resolved. Democratic erosion and regression are associated with systemic weaknesses such as fragile institutions, pervasive corruption, decaying representation and apathetic signs of public participation. Pakistan is frequently classified as a hybrid state, where power is persistently negotiated and contested between civil-military elite. Historically, the politics of Pakistan has been dominated by bureaucrats, judges, political parties and military-led alliances. Furthermore, although electoral

democracy is being practiced since 2008, but real and just popular supremacy has not been established. The military remained busy to retain power, while the judiciary acted against civilian government many times.

The main objective behind this study is to examine the reasons for decline of public trust over electoral democratic process and favorable transition towards authoritarian tendencies. The study also tries to understand that why constitutional institutions are being consolidated in such a way to arbitrarily amass personal power in developing democracies with Pakistan as focal case. The study tries to explore such elements that promote the combination of both democracy and authoritarianism in Pakistan. By analyzing the interplay between democratic and authoritarian elements, the study seeks to shed light on the complex dynamics of hybrid regimes and the structural challenges they pose to democratic consolidation.

2. Literature Review

In their research paper, Levitsky & Way (2015) examine the challenges faced by the democratic regimes during 2006 to 2015. They described the said decade as a period of democratic “erosion,” “decline” and “rollback” while mentioning that the advocates of democracy emphasize that newly emerging democracies have fallen to rising authoritarian trends. While issuing a warning about the probable consequences of democratic erosion, the authors add that the contemporary world might be at the edge of the end of democracy. In Freedom House’s annual survey, conducted in 2006, pertaining to the democratic freedoms, senior scholar Arch Puddington had also warned about the emerging democratic pushback and observed the then forthcoming period from 2007 to 2010 as years of global democratic erosion (Levitsky & Way, 2015).

Grugel (2002) provides the comprehensive detail of democratization while considering its various dimensions. He describes democratization as a transitional process from non-democratic rule to a representative government. Several other concepts have been discussed in his book including relationship of globalization with democratization and its impacts on sovereignty of the state. The book also explores democracy from historical perspective along with the causes and impacts of democratization process. Many theoretical frameworks such as ‘transition’ along with ‘moderation’ were considered responsible to boost up process of democratization (Grugel, 2002) . Although the study was conducted comprehensively and every single topic was concluded with a perspective on democratizations, nevertheless, it is partially useful for future research being insufficient for gathering of data on emerging authoritarianism.

Sadiq, Zain & Ajis (2018) identified the nature of Asian democracies with special reference to the case of Pakistan. The authors adopted qualitative and quantitative techniques to measure the prevalent situation and

condition of democratic accountability in Pakistan. They concluded that corruption and weak public service delivery are the responsible factor of failure of democracy in Pakistan. (Sadiq, Zain, & Ajis, 2018). This study is informative however some gaps have been identified in this research; while the authors discussed all issues and challenges but they did not take up the actual and fundamental causes of the decline of democracy such as gradual deterioration of civilian control over governmental institutions, involvement of military in internal and external national affairs, erosion of fundamental human freedoms and political liberties.

Taj, Nouman & Gul (2015) discussed authoritarianism in Pakistan from a historical perspective examining how it has affected the prospects and possibilities of flourishing the democracy. They argued that both India and Pakistan, after the partition was highly comparable in their potential to adopt smooth democratic process and had inherited similar administrative structure. In contrast to Pakistan, India remained more resilient to address such types of challenges (Taj, Nouman & Gul, 2015). The study did not highlight the growing threats that hinder development towards consolidated democracy in Pakistan. For example, authors discussed democratic challenges from the perspectives of local government but they did not address problems faced by the political system with respect to the Right to Information or political freedoms in Pakistan.

3. Interrelationship of Various Variables

Compiled by the Researchers

The above figure indicates the relationship between various variables devised by the current study. In the following pages, a detailed analysis of these variables and their impact on the outcome is presented:

3.1 Democratic Backsliding

Both traditional and modern version of democracies are facing serious threats from increasingly aggressive modes of authoritarian powers. In addition to these threats, liberal democratic values that have underpinned the global democratic order since the end of Cold War and collapse of Soviet Union are also under the threat both by nationalist and populist doctrines. The advancement in communication and technology along with globalization challenged the classical liberalism and traditional cultural systems. The fragile liberal political parties along with political polarization had directly been impacting the democratic principles and economic

transformations. The popular leaders mobilized politically aggrieved masses against political institutions to grab power. For instance, success of authoritarian political leaders such as Jair Bolsonaro of Brazil, Narendra Modi of India and Recep Erdogan of Turkey as well as of others across Asia, Africa, and Latin America had been closely associated with populism and manipulating skills of these leaders with respect to political polarization (Qureshi, Khan, & Lashari, 2024). Moreover, the post-World War II global order had not worked/functioned in such a way which was originally envisioned by its architectures. Thus, it is not a surprising outcome that debates related to democratic backsliding are now common in international media. It is also being felt and observed by some of the key concerned quarters that elections have no longer been regarded as a routine mechanism of bringing in a change in government but the revival of a free, transparent electoral process could rather provide the last chance to save and re-flourish the democratic norms and values. The widely available growing evidences ensure that democratic culture is in trouble and the concerns must be addressed when it feels as being threatened.

3.2 Democratic Deficit

The democratic deficit is characterized as shortfall or lack of fundamentals of democratic principles and practices alongside the state institutions which claim to follow democratic spirit. It is associated with poor institutional design, poor governance and low public engagement and participation. For instance, a decentralized model of local government exists in the constitution of Pakistan but state power is centralized which is kept and exercised at the federal and provincial levels (Sajid & Adeed, 2023).

3.3 Competitive Authoritarianism

Competitive authoritarianism is the product of post-Cold War events that, quite uniquely, envisages for full scale dictatorship. This newer version has been characterized through such a non-existent coexistence of democratic institutions that seems real but not just and fair. This model allows contesting election, tolerated political parties, opposition and civil society as well as autonomous media. The modern authoritarian rulers try to conceal autocracy while labeling their steps as taken for promotion of formal democratic institutions.

Many thinkers classified it as 'hybrid', semi-democratic, non-democratic or illiberal democratic system. Furthermore, it has been divided into various phases including partial democracy, democracy and autocracy that make its study complicated. Therefore, Levitsky & Way identified the following three classifications of democratic regimes: full-scale authoritarianism, competitive authoritarianism and democracy (Levitsky & Way, 2010). According to them, the demise of one-party system and dictatorship was expected with the end of Cold War but it did not lead to

establish democracy in most of the regions of the world including Asia, Latin America and Africa. Although, democracy formally exists in countries like Mexico, Malaysia, Nigeria, Serbia, Ukraine, Russia and Zimbabwe, nevertheless, it operates there under the shadow of competitive authoritarianism wherein unfair and unjust electoral practices prevail. They also argue that, in competitive authoritarianism, incumbent governments remain in power through manipulation of election and formal institutions of democracy are practicing there as a means to extend individual/personal controls rather than institutionalizing the exercise of political power (Carothers, 2018) . It may also be called diminished or partial form of democracy.

Furthermore, Levitsky & Way argue that the competitive authoritarianism does not always undergo transition into full-scale authoritarianism, primarily because rulers keep trying to meet with international obligation. For instance, when Justice and Development Party (AKP) in Turkey first time came into power, its leaders deliberately tried to build and pose rather softer image of the political system of the country in order to align with the mandate of the European Union (EU) (Ugur-Cinar, 2023).

3.4 Hybrid Regimes

Hybrid regimes are generally characterized by autocracies emerged through electoral triumphs germinating compromised democratic institutions and where elections are contested but fairness always remains in doubt. It neglects fundamental pre-requisites of democracy and the basic human rights like freedom of association and expression are either not met fully or respected partially. In the contemporary world, democratic values and political stability are facing serious threats as sign and symptoms of autocracy continue to emerge and grow strongly. Some scholars believe that the hybrid regimes are not a new phenomenon. It was identified and executed as model in Central Asian countries to boost up process of democratization during 1990 to 1995. Recently, Rachman described in his book that the rise of the notion of “self-style strongman” through hybrid regimes had become central pillar of the global politics. The leaderships in various capitals such as Beijing, Moscow, Ankara, Warsaw, Brasilia, Manila, Delhi and Budapest had consolidated their power under self-styled strongman. Since 1930s, the charismatic leadership has changed the dynamics and fundamentals of world politics on the basis of its performance and achievements, and almost all the countries are now under its outcomes (Levitsky & Loxton, 2014).

Compiled by the Researchers

Region	Number of Hybrid Regimes
Asia	12
Africa	14
Latin America	7
Europe	5
Middle East	10

Compiled by the Researchers

Some prominent forums involved in assessing and ranking the state of global democracy such as Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) and Freedom House indicated the existence of a number of hybrid regimes across the globe during 2024-2025. The above table shows that the African and Asian regions jointly accommodated the highest number of hybrid regimes with Africa remained at the top. The figure indicated that there exist several countries in Asian region which have blended democracy with authoritarianism and where elections are managed and compromised and their political systems lacked fairness and freedom. Pakistan, Malaysia, Thailand, Bangladesh, Cambodia, and Myanmar could have been categorized among those countries which have shadows of dynastic politics, military influence and limited consolidated democracy. As mentioned in the above figure, African region had 14 hybrid regimes in its political system out of which many had emerged in the post-colonial era. Major African countries including Ethiopia, Tanzania, Uganda, Nigeria and Kenya practice

democracy but provide limited scope of participation to the opposition political parties due to domination of ruling elite and suppressing attitude against opposition. Although, constitutional reforms and international pressure challenge the governments but the elite manipulate political patronage by undertaking clientelism. The table shows Latin American region possesses 7 hybrid regimes which represent the combination of populism and weak democratic institutions. For example, El Salvador, Nicaragua and Venezuela exhibit democratic backsliding while adopting and enforcing populist environment to capture and exercise political power in a rather centralized manner while curtailing checks and balances. Although, the elections and free media are guaranteed but systematic hurdles undermine their sustainability. Moreover, hybrid tendencies also remained present in Eastern and Southeastern European countries. The above figure shows that 5 countries are practicing hybrid model of governance including Turkey, Hungary and Serbia. These countries are facing democratic decline and backsliding owing to their illiberal policies and an excessive executive control. Although, these countries pretend to promote democratic values such as elections and a functional parliament but, in practice, suppress opposition, media and politicize the courts. The other region is Middle East having 10 such countries, including Iraq, Egypt, Lebanon, Jordan and Kuwait, which exhibit authoritarian or hybrid tendencies with the features of strong monarchy and weak or low traditions of participation.

4. Political System of Pakistan: Development and Transformation

Theoretically, Pakistan enjoys an elected democratic government but, in practice, the military has a dominant role in the overall national and governmental affairs under the political system commonly known as a 'hybrid' one. As a result, democratic process in Pakistan has become increasingly compromised. Despite the said fact, such governments are also categorized by providing little window of criticism, illegitimate behavior with political opponent and tendency to make all decision unilaterally.

In the case of Pakistan, democracy has been exploited by the dominant elite groups as a political tool to secure their status and wealth. Where civilian governments fail to respect will of the people, politicians tolerate the intervention of army to control the law and order situation. It is evident that not a single institution has been accused to detract valuable democratic process in Pakistan. Even, all partisans supported each other, ensuring the continuity of system that worked in their favor.

During 2009 to 2018, the superior judiciary delivered verdicts beyond its jurisdiction and frequently intervened in various executive and legislative affairs of government. It often overthrew executive appointments, used populist rhetoric particularly against the two mainstream political parties i.e. the Pakistan Peoples Party (PPP) and Pakistan Muslim League-

Nawaz (PML-N). The superior judiciary expanded its jurisdiction to take decision and deliberations involving such questions that who could join government and who could not? The judiciary reviewed the government decision while extending the notion that the Constitution of the country was the supreme law of the land which protected the will of the people hence the courts were using this framework to eradicate factionalism and corruption (Bajpai & Kureshi, 2022).

To strengthen the culture of democracy, both the PPP and the PML-N passed the 18th amendment which guaranteed more autonomy to provinces while accepting a greater role for them in policy making. Despite this, the high level tensions prevailed among various organs and institutions of the government such as military, ruling political parties and judiciary over executive appointments and foreign policy. As a result, political actors preferred to support an authoritarian as well as centralized state structure (Ali, 2025) . In contrast, Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaaf (PTI) advocated for constitutional and democratic institutions to delegitimize the actions of these partisan and beneficiary political actors. The party led by the charismatic leader Imran Khan, having large number of supporters from urban middle class, demonstrated the capacity to mobilize people while building a narrative to free Pakistan from the influence of corrupt dynastic political elite. The manifesto of party declared that the “legacy of misrule and misery by a corrupt, inept elite will be relegated to the dustbin of history.” Beyond such rhetoric, PTI also expanded democratic authoritarianism by using elections and demonstrations as source of democratic legitimization. Likewise, in 2017, Tehreek-e-Labaik Pakistan (TLP)’s sit-in in Islamabad over the allegation of blasphemy against government of PML-N with the endorsement of PTI further pushed the state structure to delegitimize the government of PML-N.

Similarly, some blatant disregard of the well-established constitutional spirit and structure of the 1973 Constitution was exhibited by the then incumbent coalition government of PML-N and PPP (2024) through 26th constitutional amendment along with six subsequent bills which, *inter alia*, included the expansion in the strength of the judges of Supreme Court from 17 to 34 and extending the tenure of military chiefs from three to five years. All bills had been passed from both houses very quickly and assented to by the President in the same hasty manner. This type of tactics under the shadow of democracy raised serious questions towards the overall credibility of the legislative process wherein the concerned members were apparently instructed to vote in an absolute ‘yes’ without any debate remaining at the same time unaware of the content or implications of those bills (Ahmed, 2025).

In Pakistan, it had been a discussion for most of the times and the questions had been raised about the adoption and application of western liberal democratic model that whether or not it succeeded to address the fundamental challenges faced by state of Pakistan and how the ground realities pertaining to the body politic in Pakistan could be compared to fully developed Western countries which are truly following the liberal democratic model. No doubt, democracy is the best form of government and it always satisfied the lovers of liberalism who believe in enjoying freedom in their personal and social spheres of lives. Democracy is actually rooted in the principle of humanism and its main objective is giving right to people to choose their representatives who, in turn, would act and legislate on their behalf for ensuring freedoms of the public.

In a conference which was attended by one of the authors of the instant study as well, the officials of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) raised question that what did the people of Pakistan want? The reply from the administrative/organizing staff of the event was that if democracy brought development, people would support democracy; if it did not, people would prefer development instead of preferring democracy. Mr. Touqir Hussain, one of the key organizer, further observed that Pakistan was such a state that tolerated politics led by civil-military alliance and a consequent governance structure which was contrary to the generally accepted democratic system providing for a full fledged democratic system that had to permit and ensure the public participation in political affairs. He added that millions of Pakistani people were glued to their television screen or their mobile phones following politicians every single day as if they would become serious to solve the problems of the country but people forgot that the fights of the politicians were for themselves, among themselves (Hussain, 2023).

If the question might be raised that how could such change might happen in Pakistan? While addressing this question, it must be acknowledged that it is a subject of much wider and complex debate. However, the country has numerous types of strengths such as sense of exceptionalism, incredible resilience, faith based optimism, vibrant and active media and enthusiastic civil society. Along with that, wider talent is available within some significant socio-political domains like political and social activists involved in improving activism, academia, journalists, writers and retired civil servants who had shown extraordinary interest or knowledge to bring some meaningful change in body politic of Pakistan. Besides, while effectively managing social media, the Pakistani diaspora can also inspire and mobilize the youth in Pakistan for true change and stimulate them for the sake of social movements.

The Economist Intelligence Unit, which evaluates the state of democracy around the world, reported that systematized changes incorporated into the political system of Pakistan had shifted the classification of Pakistan from a mere hybrid regime to a more authoritarian one. It further emphasized that the said assessment was accurate. Unfortunately, some scholars argue that the currently prevailing state of affairs is indistinguishable from the past; as people had often witnessed such role of military wherein it was backing or supporting one political party over other political parties and exerting influence in favor of its choice across the entire political system.

The establishment of democracy is a revolutionary change achieved through evolutionary process. However, it must be adopted with realization that it cannot resolve problems faced by the state of Pakistan by itself. Achieving meaningful democratic outcomes need to adopt tolerated political behavior that strengthens valuable democratic process. The journey towards democracy is a difficult one and closely associated to the nation and state building. The social and political movement in Europe, civil rights and progressive movements in America and Meiji Restoration revolution in Japan provided examples for such system. Thus, change does not occur because these societies become democratic, rather they become democratic since they first changed themselves. The principles of freedom, justice and equality are neither self-sustaining nor self-executing. There is no room for complacency in democracy. The democratic process in Pakistan has been pushed back in recent years but causes had been different from those as seen elsewhere. A common factor between Pakistan and other major democracies around the world is growing environment of intolerance in Pakistan which is considered a result of continuous democratic erosion. Thus, fortifying democratic values would ensure that democratic institutions are more resilient against threats to the rule of law and extra-constitutional measures that undermine political rights of the general public (Benson, 2025).

5. Comparative Features and Global Spread of Hybrid Regimes

Table: Evolution of Pakistan’s Political Classification

Compiled by the researchers

Year	Score	Regime Type
2008	5.5	Transitional Democracy
2013	5.3	Hybrid Regime
2018	4.9	Hybrid Regime
2022	4.4	Authoritarian Shift
2025	4.1	Authoritarian Category

In the above table, the score of 5.5 is assigned to the democratic era starting from the year 2008 which has been classified as a traditional democratic system wherein the elections were relatively competitive, political participation was ensured and moderation and liberties existed to some extent. Despite these facts, corruption and weaker state of the rule of law also remained existent. The era starting from year 2013 has been assigned a score of 5.3 indicating a shift of democratic process from the traditional to hybrid regime portraying mixed features of authoritarianism and democratic regime. In the said era, elections were conducted but fairness and transparency were doubtful. The culture of weaker opposition political parties and control of ruling elite had been increased. Moreover, hybrid regime was present in 2018 as well which era had been assigned a score of 4.9 as shown in the above table. In that era, civil liberties remained more curtailed as well as judicial independence and freedom of media seemed deteriorated.

The steady and speedy decline of democracy in 2022 with the assigned weightage point of 4.4 (as shown above) converted the system towards authoritarian mode. This trend increased the risk of more centralized authority with executive excessively dominated in all spheres. The score of 4.1 in 2025 ensured prevalence of authoritarianism in Pakistan showing at the same time the elimination of political pluralism and participation. This regime also highlights control of state on all political affairs, absence of competitive electoral process and independent media as well as limitation on the assurance of fundamental human rights are at the maximum.

Compiled by the researchers

Institution	Influence (%)	Nature of Control
Military	90%	Structural dominance over all political and policy domains
Judiciary	70%	Selective independence; legitimizes or restrains political actors
Political Parties	60%	Limited autonomy; dependent on approval from establishment
Civil Society	40%	Socially active but lacking and institutional Infrastructure
Media	30%	Constrained freedom; operates under indirect censorship

Compiled by the researchers

The above figure shows that the military in Pakistan is the most powerful institution, exerting nearly 90% of dominance over the decision-making infrastructure and process of the state as a whole. It also enjoys a profound influence on the matters of national security, foreign policy choices and majority of the key domestic affairs. Moving further, the Judiciary has been ranked as the second most influential institution exerting around 70% of influence with a constitutionally recognized and guaranteed independent and free decision-making structure, nevertheless, the history of the superior

courts of Pakistan reveals that the institution preferred to work in alignment with the military establishment contributing, at the same time, to democratic backsliding while applying the Doctrine of Necessity and disqualifying the then sitting Prime Ministers at various critical junctures of the constitutional and political history of Pakistan. Furthermore, the political parties with an estimated influence of 60%, contribute to the formation of hybrid regimes in Pakistan. The institutional structure and nature of mainstream political parties have been dynastic, populist and personality-driven which contributed to the weakened institutional strength whereas most of the political parties lacked internal democracy which factor encouraged the powerful quarters to frequently dismiss political governments on one pretext or the other along with undermining their capacity to rule and frame public policy freely. Interestingly, the civil society network in Pakistan which comprise over community groups, student organizations, religious bodies, NGOs, labor unions, etc., enjoy only 40 % of the influential power since it suffers institutional fragility and weakness due to its fragmented structure and limited cooperation from the state. Finally, the media has only 30% share of the influential share in the power structure of Pakistan because of the persistent censorship and oversight from the state and pressure from the regulatory bodies and state institutions which curtail freedom of expression and limit its role as a watchdog of democracy.

6. Conclusion

Unfortunately, Pakistan failed to establish a fruitful system that could pave the way of true and smooth democratic transition. The study identified several contributing factors including persistence of internal and external security challenges, entrenchment of hybrid regimes, a pervasive culture of privilege and protocol, political instability, and imitative politics.

Without timely and meaningful intervention, authoritarian tendencies may become deeply penetrated and entrenched, leading to structural changes that entirely suppress legitimate political dissent. Presently, the country is being run in such manners that lack the coherence and adherence to democratic values. If the state does not meet with the international standards such as democratic governance and liberalism, it has indulged into authoritarian tendencies where one group or institution bulldozes the mandate of others. Thus, to navigate out of this crisis, Pakistan require such level of statesmanship, not self-protecting and self-serving politicians, which would steer the nation towards democratization and inclusiveness.

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